

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article provides directions and information on the development of professional competencies of future primary school teachers, the current stage of educational reforms and modernization processes, and the need for all subjects of these processes not only to quickly accept global changes and understand their essence, but also to organize their professional activities based on an innovative approach, to quickly develop professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, and to develop professional competencies of future primary school teachers as a pedagogical problem.*

Keywords: *future primary school teachers, professional, professional competencies, development, methodology, improvement, knowledge-based society, mastery, modern requirements, scientific, higher education, institution, educational process, innovative technologies, assessment.*

INTRODUCTION

The modernization and qualitative renewal of education in our republic, the formation of modern, new models of educational institutions, indicate the need to fundamentally reconsider the requirements for the professional competence of future teachers. At the current stage of educational reforms and modernization processes, all subjects of these processes need not only to quickly accept global changes and understand their essence, but also to organize their professional activities on the basis of an innovative approach, and to quickly develop their professional knowledge, skills, and qualifications. This, in turn, will ensure that the near future activities of future teachers will be positive and competitive.

In a context where the methodological competence of future primary school teachers is constantly changing in our country, it is important to study advanced foreign experiences and develop a technology and didactic basis for developing their methodological competence in a higher educational institution, to improve pedagogical conditions, content and structure, criteria for improvement and levels of formation, form, method, means, model, and the effectiveness of teaching quality, as well as to develop theoretical and practical foundations for developing methodological competence in future primary school teachers in a higher pedagogical educational institution.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The expected result of training students in higher educational institutions of pedagogical education is formulated in the form of requirements for mastering the main educational programs presented through general cultural, general professional and professional competencies. The state educational standards also define the profile (specialty) competence of the future teacher, which is an important component of the teacher's professional competence. Currently, it is one of the least studied problems. One of these issues is to identify a competency-based approach to the

development of professional competencies in future primary school teachers and develop its structural model in accordance with the basic provisions of the State Educational Standards. In order to determine the professional competence of a future primary school teacher, we will focus on some studies devoted to the study of this concept. Studies that have studied professional competence as a pedagogical problem have mainly analyzed the characteristics of the teacher.

Our article scientifically explains the need to develop professional competencies based on modern requirements in order to adequately master the changes in the "knowledge-based society" in improving the methodology for developing professional competencies of future primary school teachers. This development implies deep systemic changes in the teaching process of higher educational institutions that will positively affect the purpose, content, innovative technologies, assessment and results of education.

These changes expand the possibilities for improving the methodology for developing the professional competencies of future primary school teachers for today and the future. In order to broadly substantiate the essence of our article and prove the relevance of its pedagogical necessity, we also analyzed foreign best practices. In November 2002, in Copenhagen (Denmark), the Copenhagen Declaration of the Ministers of Education of European countries on the development of cooperation in the field of vocational education and training in Europe was adopted, according to which the main goal was to create a system of advanced training of specialists, a mechanism for mutual recognition of professional competencies and qualifications; to develop mechanisms for recognizing competencies in different countries and at different levels by developing common principles of certification.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The problem of increasing the level of professional competence of a future teacher, who has the ability to think freely and actively, model the educational process, develop and implement new ideas and technologies of teaching and upbringing, is relevant in modern socio-economic conditions.

The main conditions for developing the professional competence of future teachers are:

1) organizational and managerial (creating a curriculum, a schedule of the educational process, a lesson schedule, developing criteria for determining the level of competence, material and technical support of the educational process);

2) educational-methodological (selection of the content of classes, integration of different courses, identification of leading ideas);

3) technological (control and evaluation, organization of active forms of teaching, identification of knowledge groups included in the competence, application of innovative technologies);

4) psychological-pedagogical (diagnosis of student development, stimulation of motivation for learning, determination of criteria for competence, directing students to work in collaboration).

The structure of a future teacher's professional competence is determined by his or her pedagogical skills, and skills (knowledge based on theoretical knowledge and aimed at solving pedagogical problems) are determined by a set of gradually developing actions.

The European Education Foundation (ETF) defines competence as follows [3]: the ability to perform a task effectively; to meet the requirements for employment; to be able to carry out a specific professional activity. The European project "Identification and Classification of Key Competences" (DeSeCo) considers competences as "factors for the effective functioning of

society and life success” [1]. The Council of Europe has developed several definitions of the term competence [4]: political and social competences, such as the ability to take responsibility, participate in the decision-making process of a team or group, conflict management, dispute resolution, and participate in the improvement of democratic institutions; communication competences, which are particularly important for work and social life; skills in using and critically evaluating information related to the informatization of society; and lifelong learning competences in the context of personal, professional, and social activities.

The Education 2030 project of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) is conducting a comparative analysis of global educational programs to develop a universal model of professional competencies [5]. The Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21) has developed a framework of competencies for the 21st century called the Four Cs – Collaboration; Communication; Critical Thinking; Creativity – in its research on developing 21st century competencies necessary for successful functioning in a digital society [3].

The Canadian government has adopted a new approach to developing competencies for the school curriculum, according to which the following group of competencies has been formed [4]: character education (the ability to act constructively in changing and uncertain conditions, values of perseverance, adaptability, personal development); citizenship education (civic literacy); collaboration; creativity; communication; critical thinking and problem solving.

Finland's national education standards reflect 7 competencies [3]: participation in building a sustainable future; thinking, learning to read; cultural competencies, cooperation, communication; self-care, organizing daily life; multiliteracies; IT literacy; career and entrepreneurship.

In the USA, Harvard University in Cambridge has developed the Negotiation and Leadership program [1], which aims to develop the following competencies: leadership skills; mastery of negotiation technologies; negotiation concepts and methods; emotion management; mediation in negotiations; mediation technologies; conflict management.

The Center for Competency Development and Validation of Saint Petersburg University of Economics [2] offers professional and universal competencies through a “multi-stage competency validation program”.

The UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) has developed a global digital competence framework [1].

The European Commission's Joint Research Centre presents the following system of competencies [6]: information literacy (searching and filtering data and digital content, evaluating digital content, managing data); communication and collaboration (collaboration through digital technologies, communication, information exchange, networking, digital identity); digital content creation (digital content development, content processing, copyright, licenses, programming); security (device protection, personal data protection, environmental protection); problem solving (solving technical problems, identifying needs and technological responses, creative use of digital technologies).

CONCLUSION

Today, in the process of implementing the requirements of the "Law on Education"[1], the training of highly qualified pedagogical personnel is being put on the agenda as an important issue. Therefore, based on these requirements, the training of knowledgeable, independent thinkers, creative seekers, highly qualified, cultured, and experts in various fields is an urgent problem.

Among the conditions that guarantee the development of a new model of personality recognized in the law, its development into a person with deep knowledge, and its perfection, it seems that the methods and rules of psychology are not enough to apply the teacher's professional and methodological competence to educational and upbringing processes. Accordingly, it is necessary to study the development trends in the younger generation's educational periods, to study how new teaching technologies are mastered by the learner and how they affect his mental and intellectual abilities, and to combine psychological methods with didactic methods. This requires a high level of methodological competence from the future teacher, especially socio-psychological competence related to the ability to correctly assess the psychology of the learner and the teacher in different conditions.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that there is a dynamic of research on the development and improvement of competencies by international organizations and research institutes, which justifies the priority of studying the problem of our study as a pedagogical problem.

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